

FACTORS AFFECTING INCREASING THE PROFITABILITY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE TERRITORY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article provides information about the factors affecting the increase in the profitability of industrial enterprises in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their solutions.

Key words: industrial sectors, economic proportions, profitability, economic regions.

Determining the long-term development of the industry requires determining and paying attention to various economic ratios. Such proportions are taken into account when forecasting the network structure.

Planning and forecasting of the industrial production structure should focus on solving the following main issues:

1. To determine the rate of development of the industry as a whole and any of its branches, taking into account the requirements of the market economy, the national economy and the population's demand for certain types of products;
2. Identifying advanced production industries, allocating capital investments and materials necessary to accelerate their development;
3. Priority changes in the industrial structure should be considered so that any such changes ensure the highest efficiency of social production;
4. The general balance of the national economy requires a connection with the equality of the development of each industry.

Facilitation of the network structure at the country level ensures high-speed economic development, raising the standard of living of the population and reducing the costs of production. Because it causes an increase in the level of production and the final, provard product, generally positive structural changes. Therefore, the structural change itself appears as an additional factor in the growth of production efficiency and labor productivity.

The main ways to improve the structure of industrial networks are as follows:

- establishing a balance between industries that produce means of production and consumer goods;
- development of forecasts and trends of the production structure;
- stabilization of foreign economic activities of branches;
- acceleration of scientific and technical development, introduction of advanced technologies;
- study of personal and social consumption and full supply of high-quality industrial products to the population;
- to increase the efficiency of rational use of raw materials and resources in networks.[3]

To provide the industry of economic regions with the necessary (labor, material and financial) resources and ensure their rational use.

At the same time, it will be necessary to solve the tasks of restructuring the internal structure of industries, increasing production and living standards of the population, economic

cooperation with foreign enterprises, directing foreign investments and advanced technologies to the production of high-quality industrial goods.

The structural changes taking place in the republic's economy and its leading branch of industry will create opportunities for the following in the near future:

- ensuring the satisfaction of the country's population's needs for food products, goods in popular demand and other vital means;
- the development of technologies that save scientific and technical progress and the advancing development of industry, advanced industries in general;
- to increase the products produced in the republic itself and reduce the import of goods on this basis;
- increasing the efficiency of the agro-industrial complex and transferring it to further processing of agricultural raw materials and improving the quality and appearance of the finished product;
- creation of new jobs and new industries based on the development of small business enterprises (firms and entrepreneurship, farmers, farms, production structures of the "enterprise-neighborhood" type);
- and finally, taking into account the availability of appropriate conditions and mineral resources for the production of this or that product in the republic, it creates conditions for increasing the export potential of the industry and achieving export superiority.

The profitability indicator is one of the main indicators of industrial enterprise performance evaluation.

Profitability characterizes the level of profitability of the enterprise. Usually, several types of it are included in the book. It can be determined by the form of direct property, by the source of income or by the basis, by the units affecting the change of profit or by the independent units.

Factors affecting profitability change are given special importance in the analysis. Factors affecting the change in profitability can be determined in relation to the units involved in them. For example, if the change in profitability in relation to the sale of products is affected by the change in the amount of gross profit from sales and the change in the amount of revenue received from sales, the profitability of fixed assets is affected by the change in the net profit of the enterprise and the change in the average annual value of fixed assets, the total profitability is the amount of net profit corresponding to one amount of revenue changes, changes in the turnover of fixed assets and changes in the turnover of tangible assets are affected, etc.

Profitability indicator is taken as a measuring tool for evaluating the activity of the enterprise and its effectiveness. It can also be called an indicator of measuring the effectiveness of direct activity.

The classification of factors according to the sources of increasing production efficiency helps to determine whether social labor savings can be achieved or achieved at the expense of what. From this point of view, the following factors can be included in the main factors: product labor capacity, material capacity, fund capacity and reduction of demand for capital funds, rational use of natural resources and saving time. But such a classification does not meet the requirement. In order to find answers to these questions, it is necessary to group all factors of increasing production efficiency according to the main directions of production development and improvement. They consist of a complex of technical, organizational, economic and social

measures aimed at saving social labor. These directions are very diverse. The most important ones include:

- improvement of production structure;
- acceleration of scientific and technical development, raising the technical and economic level of production and products, shortening the period of introduction of scientific and technical achievements;
- increasing the level of production specialization, cooperation, combination and regional deployment;
- improvement of management structure, financing, assessment and crediting and incentive system;
- to increase the creative activity and initiative of workers on the basis of strengthening the human factor.[1]

Liberalization of industrial production and deepening of reforms in this sector is the main direction of increasing efficiency.

Another crucial way to increase the efficiency of industrial production is the acceleration of scientific and technical progress. The technical and technological factor provides at least two-thirds of labor productivity growth.

It is known that the nature and content of technical development at different stages of economic development has its own characteristics. For example, as a result of the transition to a market economy, scientific and technical progress is focused not only on quantitative changes, but more on qualitative changes. In general, efficiency is related to quality changes in the economy, this requirement is fully introduced to the development of science and technology.

The role of the human factor in raising the socio-economic efficiency of industrial production to a high level is incomparable. People's initiative, energy, and creativity are the most important and powerful source of any development. That is why they say that man is the main productive force of society. It creates all innovations, including new, advanced techniques and technologies, rationally organizes production, makes scientific and practical discoveries. All means of production are set in motion by human labor, and useful things are created. However, man is not only the main productive force, but also the subject of production and other social relations. Human activity is realized through these relationships. The direction and results of this activity depend on the thoughts, ideas, goals, life guidelines, goals and psychological beliefs of the employee in his work. Therefore, when analyzing the essence, significance and content of the human factor, it should be discussed not only about the person, but also about the social qualities, factors that stimulate activity and conditions determined by the whole system of social relations in which a person lives and works.

A number of other principles can be widely used in the management of branches, enterprises and other areas of industrial production. These include:

- unity in leadership and management;
- connecting planning with market requirements in the management process;
- principle of stability;
- the principle of material and moral stimulation of work;
- principle of scientificity;
- principle of economy;

- the principle of selecting and placing personnel.

A number of general philosophical methods can also be used in the management of industrial production. In order to study and analyze the secrets of industrial management on a scientific basis, the following methods are widely used:

1. Systematic approach
2. Comprehensive approach
3. Structural approach
4. Situational approach
5. Integration approach
6. Modeling approach
7. Economic mathematical approach
8. Method of observation
9. Experimental method

Dozens of independent sectors and thousands of enterprises (firms) are operating under the management of Uzbekistan's industry. Developing each of them, coordinating with each other, placing them in the republic, determining the demand for products (performance of work and providing services) and solving other very complex and comprehensive issues in a timely manner. requires the implementation of network management. For this reason, a number of branch offices are established. These include:

- ministries and state committees;
- concerns and corporations, unions and associations;
- holding and national companies;
- enterprises (firms) and others.

Ministries are considered an integral part of the Cabinet of Ministers, they lead all enterprises (firms) and organizations subordinate to them in all regions of Uzbekistan.

Therefore, the Ministry is the highest level of management in the economic system of the sector it belongs to. He is responsible for the following activities:

- the condition of the network, its further development;
- selection, deployment, training and protection of personnel;
- the size, quality and competitiveness of the produced product;
- to meet internal and external demand for the product;
- and finally, he is responsible for organizing and strengthening the relations of his own enterprises with foreign countries. [2]

Rational management of industrial production has always had a great impact on the further development and strengthening of the national economy of the country and will have a sufficient impact in the future.

Conclusion:

Industry is the main and leading branch of material production. The emergence and development of industry leads to an increase in the number of workers and an increase in their status in society. When talking about the avant-garde role of workers in the historical renewal of society during the period of independence, it can be said that only the working class can help unite and consolidate the masses of workers and protect, strengthen and ensure independence. This opinion is confirmed by the reality of Uzbekistan every day. The worker of Uzbekistan forms the main part of the gross social product of the republic, the

national income, actively participates in raising the socio-economic potential of the country to a high level.

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